

Clinicopathological Study of Lower Limb Cellulitis: A Retrospective Study from a Tertiary Care Hospital in a Coastal District of OdishaLachhman Bag¹, Dillip Kumar Chand², Dibyajyoti Sahoo³, Jyotiranjana Mohapatra⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, Odisha.²Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, Odisha.³Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, Odisha.⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, Odisha.

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Abstract:**Background:** Cellulitis is a non-necrotizing inflammation of the dermis and subcutaneous tissues. It is scarcely reported in medical literature.**Aim and Objective:** To document the clinicopathological details of lower limb cellulitis at a tertiary care hospital in Odisha.**Materials and Methods:** This study investigated patients admitted with lower limb cellulitis between January 2022 and December 2023. We analyzed their medical records to understand factors like age, gender, underlying conditions, symptoms, treatment received, and treatment success.**Results:** One hundred nine (109) patients with lower limb cellulitis were admitted during the study period. Of these patients, 56 (51.3%) were males and 43(48.6%) were females. The mean age of the patients was 46.6 years (standard deviation 19.2). Among males, the majority (39%) were in their Fifth decade of life, while the majorities (41%) of females were in their fourth decade. The most of the cases were particularly among people in field jobs 57(52%). All patients presented with swelling of the lower limb, with 54(49.5%) having swelling in the left leg and 49(45%) in the right leg. followed by diabetes mellitus and smoking. The mean duration of swelling before admission was 13 days (SD 3.9). Over half 45(41.3%) of the cases were managed conservatively (Antibiotic treatment) resulted in complete resolution. However, complications occurred in 62(56.9%) of cases, requiring surgical intervention. Abscess formation was the most frequent complication, observed in 45(41.3%) of cases. The average hospital stay in this study was 8.2 ± 1.3 days.**Conclusion:** Lower limb cellulitis had a high complication rate influenced by duration of symptoms prior to hospitalization and antibiotic therapy.**Keywords:** Lower limb, Cellulitis, Socciodemographic characteristics, Risk factors.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Cellulitis is a non-necrotizing inflammation of the dermis and subcutaneous tissues of the skin. It is typically caused by an acute bacterial infection. While cellulitis can occur anywhere on the body, the lower limbs are most commonly affected, with reported rates ranging from 58% to 98%. The face, hands, torso, neck, and buttocks are less frequently affected, in that order [1,2,3].

Several risk factors contribute to cellulitis, including traumatic injury, leg ulcers, intertrigo, overweight, lymphedema, diabetes mellitus, vasculitis, prior surgery, radiotherapy, and immune-compromised states [3]. Common causative organisms for cellulitis are *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, followed by beta-hemolytic streptococci and gram-negative bacilli [4]. The exact

incidence of cellulitis in India is unknown, but in the USA, it is a common infection affecting 2-3 people per 100 people per year. Stulberg et al. described the clinical hallmarks of cellulitis as warmth, erythema, edema with non-palpable margins and tenderness of the affected area, along with associated lymphangitis, regional lymphadenopathy, and fever [5].

Lower limb cellulitis is a common cause of hospitalization, leading to significant morbidity, healthcare costs, and economic loss [6]. Delayed reporting of symptoms is known to contribute to frequent hospital admissions, potentially resulting in delayed diagnosis and serious complications. A recent publication by The Lancet Commission on Global Surgery highlights that over 5 billion people

worldwide lack access to safe, timely, and affordable surgical care when needed. This burden is greatest in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [7].

The problem is likely to worsen as preventable diseases like cellulitis continue to be a reason for hospitalization. With limited existing literature on cellulitis in Odisha, this study aims to describe the demographic characteristics, clinical presentation, treatment modalities, and outcomes for patients admitted with lower limb cellulitis.

Materials and Methods

This hospital based retrospective study was conducted on all patients who admitted to the Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri with a diagnosis of lower limb cellulitis between January 2022 and December 2023.

Patients with a discharge diagnosis of lower limb cellulitis were included in the study, while those with cellulitis in other areas were excluded. Using a data abstraction form, we collected data on patient demographics, risk factors, clinical presentation, treatment modality, and outcome of cellulitis by reviewing their history, physical examination, and laboratory records.

Data obtained was entered into a Microsoft excel. The results of the data analysis were reported as proportions using frequencies and percentages. A Pearson chi-square test was used to determine the degree of significant relationship between some variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The study used secondary data, ensuring no direct contact or intervention with any patients.

Results

One hundred nine (109) patients with lower limb cellulitis were admitted during the study period. Of these patients, 56(51.3%) were males and 53(48.6%) were females resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1:1. The mean age of the patients was 46.6 years (standard deviation 19.2). Among males, the majority (39%) were in their Fifth decade of life, while the majorities (41%) of females were in their fourth decade. The most of the cases were particularly among people in field jobs 57(52%). Among the patients, 91 (83.4%) were married. Nearly (20.1%) of the patients had no formal education. Majority of patients (64 patients, 58.71%) presented during harvesting season of June to September (Table 1)

Table 1: The socio-demographic details of patients having lower limb cellulitis.

Sociodemographic characteristics		Frequency (N=109)	%
Age	≤20	1	0.92
	30-40	18	16.51
	41-50	37	33.94
	51-60	13	11.93
	61-70	17	15.60
	71-80	14	12.84
	≥81	9	8.26
Sex	Male	56	51.38
	Female	53	48.62
Occupation	Farmer	31	28.44
	Labourer	26	23.85
	Desk job	14	12.84
	Student	3	2.75
	Unemployed	7	6.42
	Housewife	28	25.19
Education	None	23	21.1
	Others (infants)	0	0
	Basic	36	33.03
	Secondary	32	29.36
	Tertiary	18	16.51
Marital Status	Married	91	83.49
	Unmarried /Single	18	16.51

The underlying factors such as disrupted skin barrier 76 (69.7%), and toe-web intertrigo 84 (77.1%) were the most frequently encountered (Table 2).

Table 2: The underlying risk factors of lower limb cellulitis.

Risk factors		Frequency (N=109)	%
Obesity (BMI >30)	Yes	27	24.8
	No	82	75.2
History of diabetes	Yes	43	39.4
	No	66	60.6
History of cellulitis	Yes	14	12.8
	No	95	87.2
History of hypertension	Yes	44	40.4
	No	65	59.6
Alcohol consumption	Yes	42	38.5
	No	67	61.5
History of smoking	Yes	34	31.2
	No	75	68.8
Current smoker	Yes	31	28.4
	No	78	71.6
History of disruption of skin barrier	Yes	76	69.7
	No	33	30.3
History of surgery to the lower limb	Yes	51	46.8
	No	58	53.2
Presence of toe-web intertrigo	Yes	84	77.1
	No	25	22.9

All the patients presented with swelling of the lower limb involving the left lower limb in 54(49.5%) and right in 49 (45%) cases. Bilateral lower limbs were involved in 6 patients (5.5%). The commonest region of the lower limb involved was the leg in 61 (56%) followed by the foot in 42 (38.5%). All the patients had pain in the affected lower limb 94 (86.2%) of the patients presented with redness but

was absent in 15(13.8%) patients [Figure 1]. These findings are shown in Table 3.

The mean duration of swelling before admission was 13 days (SD 3.9). Eighty-Six patients (78.89%) could not walk on the affected limb. Only 3.6% (4 patients) developed cellulitis spontaneously without an identifiable local risk factor.

Table 3. Clinical Presentation of lower limb cellulitis.

Clinical Presentation		Frequency (N=109)	%
Leg Laterality	Left	54	49.5
	Right	49	45.0
	Bilateral	6	5.5
Area of lower limb involved	Thigh	2	1.8
	Leg	61	56.0
	Foot	42	38.5
	Knee	0	0.0
	Whole limb	6	5.5
Pain	Present	103	94.5
	Absent	6	5.5
Redness	Present	94	86.2
	Absent	15	13.8
Swelling	Yes	109	100.0
	No	0	0.0
Loss of function	Yes	86	78.9
	No	23	21.1

Figure 1. Cellulitis of left leg

Following antibiotic treatment, 47 (43.1%) cases fully resolved without complications, while 62 (56.9%) developed complications. Surgical treatment was carried out in 64 (58.7%) of patients who had complications. As shown in Table 4, the most frequent complications were abscess (45 cases, 41.3%), followed by ulcer (32 cases, 29.4%).

The surgeries performed included debridement (61, 55.9%), incision and drainage (36, 33%), and minor (Ray) amputations (9, 8.2%). Gangrene, a complication of cellulitis, was observed in three patients (2.8%) who underwent Ray amputation of the 2nd and 4th toes of the left foot, respectively. The mean length of hospital stay was 7.52 days (SD 5.029).

Table 4: Treatment outcomes and complications of patients presented lower limb cellulitis.

Treatment details		Frequency (N=100)	%
Mode of treatment	Conservative	45	41.3
	Surgery	64	58.7
Treatment outcome	Recovered	47	43.1
	Recovered with Complications	62	56.9
Complications	Abscess	45	41.3
	Necrotizing soft tissue infection	18	16.5
	Ulcer	32	29.4
	Gangrene	3	2.8
	Septic shock	9	8.3

Discussion

Cellulitis is a non-necrotizing infection of the skin and subcutaneous tissues. It most commonly affects the lower limbs and typically strikes older adults, with the incidence rising significantly with age [6]. In an Indian study, the mean age of patients affected by cellulitis was 36.4 ± 1.23 years [8]. Similarly, a study done at Department of Family and Preventive Medicine, University of Utah School of Medicine, [9] revealed that 21 to 44 years age group was most affected. In our study, the mean age of the patients was 46.6 years (standard deviation 19.2). However, in sub-Saharan Africa, the disease tends to affect younger patients [10]. A study found that the most common age group for lower limb cellulitis was 30-39 years old, with an average age of 38.8 years.

Ellis Simonsen et al. [9] also found the incidence of cellulitis more in males (35.7/1000 person years) as compared with females (34.5/1000 person years). In a study, cellulitis was more commonly seen in males, 46 (76.6%), as compared with females, 14 (23.3%), [8] While Nijmi et al. [10] found majority of cases in Female. In this study we also found male predominance and among males, the majorities (39%) were in their fifth decade of life, while the majorities (41%) of females were in their fourth decade.

Most patients in this study had either basic education or no formal education. As observed in this study, people of low socioeconomic status tend to delay seeking hospital care, which can often lead to higher complication rates. The role played by local risk

factors in the development of cellulitis of the leg should be elucidated.

In a study done by Deshpande et al.,[11] farmers were most commonly affected by cellulitis (77.7%), followed by laborers (11.5%), and housewives were least affected (0.8%). Similarly, in this study, people involved in field job-like mechanics, laborers, and farmers were most affected. Injuries due to farm injuries are a peculiar risk factor for farmers and there is a need to train rural population to take safety measures including protective shoes and gloves.

Obesity, diabetes mellitus, history of cellulitis, immunosuppression, lymphedema, peripheral vascular disease, voluntary cosmetic depigmentation, disruption in cutaneous barrier, toe-web intertrigo and leg ulcers have been identified as risk factors of cellulitis in previous studies [12]; with toe-web intertrigo and disruption in skin barrier 68.8% followed by presence of diabetes (52%), obesity (56.3%), hypertension (44.7%), history of smoking (47.4%), and alcohol [10]. In this study, disruption in the skin barrier and presence of toe-web intertrigo were strongly associated with cellulitis reaffirming the role played by local risk factors in the development of cellulitis of the leg.

All the patients in this study presented with unilateral swelling of the lower limb, over half of them on the right. The leg was the most common location of the lower limb with cellulitis similar to findings by Kenche et al.,[13] in rural India.

In a study done at Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Wardha, Maharashtra, India, it was observed that leg was the most common part of lower limb involved in cellulitis (55.38%), which matches with the findings of our study [9].

The average duration of noticing symptoms to presentation at the hospital was 13 days (SD 3.9) days and over a half of patients reported after 5 days of noticing symptoms. Late presentation is a major reason for high complication rate and a cause of frequent hospital admission. Outpatient management of cellulitis is less expensive and preferred by patients, and this outpatient management has been advocated for in some studies [14]. However, this can only be possible if patients report early and there is prompt treatment.

Complication rate for cellulitis is generally between 8.9 to 47.4% worldwide [15]. These complications were ulcers, tissue necrosis, abscesses and gangrene. Our complication rate was higher than reported in previous studies [10, 15, 16]. The delay in seeking medical treatment has been identified as a cause of worse outcomes in cellulitis, as was observed in this study.

Deshpande et al.,[11] where 46 (35.38%) patients needed surgery with 25 (19.23%) patients requiring debridement, 18 (13.84%) patients underwent incision and drainage, and only 1 (0.76%) landed up with amputation. Similarly, in another study done by Njim et al.,[10] 4.92% of the patients had to undergo amputation.

More than half of the patients underwent surgical treatment for their complications and highest amongst them was surgical debridement. Our findings are consistent with other findings where surgery was indicated for majority of cases with cellulitis [16] but contrary to that of Mzabi et al.,[1] who reported a very low rate of surgical management. This is probably due to the relative late reporting of patients in this study for treatment. It is possible that indiscriminate prescription of antibiotics as well as high use for self-medication at home with the final endpoint, amongst others, of antibiotic resistance; likely contributed to observed poor response to treatment, need for surgery and thus long hospital stays.

Conclusion

Cellulitis is a subcutaneous spreading bacterial infection that is more common in males. Its incidence is highest among the working-age population. Because the leg is the most commonly affected area of the lower limb, people with conditions like venous ulcers, eczema, and leg lymphedema should receive treatment for these conditions, as they predispose individuals to cellulitis. Additionally, smoking and alcohol consumption should be avoided, and co-morbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and obesity must be controlled, as they can worsen the severity of cellulitis and increase the risk of complications.

Cellulitis carries a high complication rate, significantly influenced by the duration of symptoms before hospitalization and antibiotic treatment. Early hospital reporting is recommended to reduce morbidity and associated costs. Patients should be aware of signs of severe infection, such as violaceous bullae, cutaneous hemorrhage, skin anesthesia, sloughing, and loss of peripheral pulses. These signs indicate a higher risk of surgical intervention, prolonged hospitalization, and increased morbidity. To prevent such complications, patients should seek medical attention before these signs develop. Finally, we recommend larger multicenter studies to better characterize the national burden of cellulitis.

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